

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Slurry Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Slurry Concentrator

to enhance the efficiency of soil nutrient application

Challenge

Manure management is a significant challenge for farmers, particularly those operating small to medium-sized farms. Solutions are needed to improve their use of fertilisers and potentially export them to nutrient-poorer areas.

Solid-liquid separators address this challenge by producing liquid and solid fractions. However, the different machinery needed for each fraction complicates soil application, resulting in heavy machinery investment for farmers and difficulty in monitoring nutrient application.

Optimal to be applied to distant fields where nutrients are not available

Applied in nearby fields, where there is a surplus of nutrients.

Results

- **Increased Efficiency:** The innovative system yields two liquid fractions: a semi-liquid phase (concentrating the organic matter and nutrients) to be transported and applied to distant fields where nutrients are not available; and a liquid phase (with a low nutrient concentration) to be applied in a nearby fields.
- **Cost Savings:** Using the same equipment for both fractions reduces both investment and operating costs, while also decreasing the time required for management.
- **Enhanced Monitoring and Precision:** The system enables easier monitoring of applied nutrients to the soil, as online devices can track the nutrient content of the liquid fraction. This facilitates precision fertilisation, minimises nutrient losses and reduces emissions, thereby optimising soil health and productivity.

The equipment used to manage the two fractions is the same (tractor with a pump and a slurry tanker) which reduces investment costs, but also operating costs.

View of the concentrator

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